

Frequency Analysis of Myanmar Bamboo Xylophone (Pattalar)

Htee Mu Wah* , Thinzar Wut Yee**

Abstract

Myanmar Bamboo Xylophone (Pattalar) is one of the famous Myanmar fixed-pitch musical instruments. In this paper, the frequency contents such as, pitch, harmonics and their relative amplitude of individual note of Pattalar are analyzed by Fourier analysis. The frequencies changing over time, in other words time-frequency representation of each tone, is visualized by spectrogram method based on short time Fourier transform (STFT). The music interval between two successive notes is computed in Cents and the resulting measurements are compared with the tuning of the Myanmar classical songs recorded by Burma Research Society (BRS).

Keywords: STFT, Spectrogram, Pattalar, BRS, Cents.

Introduction

Bamboo Xylophone (Pattalar) is a famous Myanmar musical instrument made by Waboe Bamboo. Under the Bamboo slats, there is a wooden resonator to produce a pleasant sound. It has its own unique sound and traditional tuning. Pattalar has seven notes for an octave and tempered to the diatonic scale. However, some of the notes E*, A* and B* of Myanmar music scale are the neutral tones and they are a quarter tone lower than the western diatonic [Muriel C Williamson, 2000]. A Pattalar consists of three octaves and all together 24 notes. In this paper, the numerical data of pitch of individual note are computed and studied the tuning of Pattalar in the scientific perspective. In musical acoustic, the distance between the two pitches or the music interval between them can be measured in units called cents, mathematically expressed as

$$cents = 1200 \log_2 \left(\frac{f_1}{f_2} \right) = 3986 \times \log_{10} \left(\frac{f_1}{f_2} \right)$$

Where, f_1 and f_2 are the frequencies of the successive lower and upper notes [Muriel C Williamson, 2000]. The tuning is compared with the old tuning obtained by the recorded classical songs of Burma Research Society (BRS) just before World War Two (ca. 1945), posted in a website called Myanmar Gandawin Thichins (Myanmar Classical Songs). The time-frequency representation and harmonic contents and of the sound are analyzed and visualized by a spectrogram.

Short Time Fourier Transform

The Fourier transform is the algorithm to transforming the time domain waveform to the frequency spectrum. The discrete spectrum $X(k)$ of periodic signals are computed by discrete Fourier transform (DFT). The general equation for discrete Fourier transform is,

$$X(k) = \sum_{n=-N/2}^{N/(2-1)} x(n) e^{-j\omega_k n}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$$

Where, ω is the discrete radian frequency, n is the discrete time indexing in samples and k is the discrete frequency index in bins [Li Tan, 2008].

* Assistant lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University

** Dr., Demonstrator, Department of Physics, Bago University

The sounds of the musical instruments are not periodic and time-varying waveforms, therefore the short time Fourier transform (STFT) is the most appropriate way to capture time varying sinusoids. The common equation for short time Fourier transform (STFT) is

$$X_l(k) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} w(n)x(n+lH)e^{-j\omega_k n} \quad l = 0, 1, \dots$$

Where, $w(n)$ is the analysis window, l is the frame number and H is the hop-size of time advance of the window. The spectrum $X_l(k)$ is a function of two variables, the frame number l and the discrete frequency index k . The window-type, window-length, hop-size and FFT-size are the important parameters of the STFT [Julius O. Smith III, 2011].

Windowing the signal is the first step in computing STFT. Type of the window is mainly determined by the width of the main lobe and the highest side-lobe level, which measures how many dB down the highest side lobe is from the main lobe. The window length are determined by,

$$M \geq B_s \frac{f_s}{|f_{k+1} - f_k|}$$

Where, B_s is the main lobe bandwidth, f_s is the sampling rate and M is the window length. The FFT-size N is chosen to be the power of two and at least twice the window length. The hop-size is the analysis of how much time origin is advanced from frame to frame. Based on the concept of STFT the power spectrum and spectrogram of the sound signal are computed. In this work, a blackman window with the window length of 1023 samples, 2048 samples of FFT size and 250 samples hop size are used for STFT analysis.

Result and Discussion

The numerical data of fundamental frequency and the computation value of music scale for three different Pattalars are described in table (1). This table is only for the middle octave and they are followed the diatonic scale. However some note varied between musical significant pitch changes ± 25 cents reported by Muriel C Williamson. Especially, E*4 of Dr Maung Maung Kha Pattalar and A*4 of Yu(1) and Yu(2) are closed to western diatonic. Table (2) is the frequency tuning and music scale of three different songs recorded from BRS, BRS_02, BRS_08, BRS_10. In this table, D4 and A*4 of BRS_02, G4 of BRS_08 and F4 and B*4 of BRS_10 varied from the musical scale closed to a semitone. Therefore the tuning of Pattalar are not consistent.

Figure (1) is the waveform of C4 or of 1-Pauk2 notes two different sources, figure 1(a) is the 1-Pauk2 note recorded from Dr Maung Maung Kha Pattalar and figure 1(b) is the 1-Pauk2 note obtained from BRS_02 song (ဝဲနဲနဲဝဲနဲဝဲနဲ). Similarly, Figure (2) is the power spectrum of these two notes and Figure (3) the spectrogram. In figure (1) the waveform of these two notes is not identical. In figure (2) although the fundamental frequency has the same value, the shape of the power spectrum, the numbers of harmonics and the amplitude level are not the same. In figure (3) there is also a different spectrogram although the same parameters of the window length, window type, FFT size and hop size.

Table(1) Frequencies Tuning and Music Intervals Measured from Three Different Pattalars

Notes Western	Notes Myanmar	Frequency (Hz) Dr MMK	Interval (Cents)	Frequency (Hz) Yu (1)	Interval (Cents)	Frequency (Hz) Yu (2)	Interval (Cents)
C5	1-Pauk3	516	1184	527	1199	524	1177
B*4	2-Pauk2	490	1095	494	1088	493	1072
A*4	3-Pauk2	432	877	444	904	447	903
G4	4-Pauk2	385	678	395	702	397	698
F4	5-Pauk2	352	523	348	483	350	480
E*4	6-Pauk2	329	407	328	381	325	352
D4	7-Pauk2	289	183	296	204	295	185
C4	1-Pauk2	260	0	263	0	265	0

Dr MMK The recorded of Dr Maung Maung Kha Pattalar

Yu(1) The recorded of one of the unknown Pattalar at Yangon University

Yu(2) The recorded of one others Pattalar at Yangon University

Table(2) Frequencies Tuning and Music Intervals Measured from Three Different Songs BRS_02, BRS_08, BRS_10

Notes Western	Notes Myanmar	Frequency (Hz) BRS_02	Interval (Cents)	Frequency (Hz) BRS_08	Interval (Cents)	Frequency (Hz) BRS_10	Interval (Cents)
C5	1-Pauk3	529	1212	540	1228	539	1161
B*4	2-Pauk2	482	1051	484	1039	483	972
A*4	3-Pauk2	470	1008	431	839	451	854
G4	4-Pauk2	386	668	421	799	408	681
F4	5-Pauk2	352	509	353	495	353	431
E*4	6-Pauk2	321	350	323	342	328	304
D4	7-Pauk2	319	340	290	156	306	184
C4	1-Pauk2	262	0	265	0	275	0

BRS_02 ပုံနှုန်းဝတ်ကြိုး (ပတ္တလား-ဆရာနွဲ့၊ ဆို-ဒေါလီညွန့်)

BRS_08 ခေါ်ပါယောင်ဝတ်တော်ရုံဘွဲ့ (ပတ္တလား-ဆရာမောင်၊ ဆို-ဒေါ်စောမြအေးကြည်)

BRS_10 ကြောက်ဖွယ်ဘုန်းတန်းကြိုး (ပတ္တလား-ဆရာမောင်၊ ဆို-ဒေါ်စောမြအေးကြည်)

Figure (1) The wave form of 1-Pauk2 notes (a) 1-Pauk2 Note of Dr Maung Maung kha Pattalar (b) 1-Pauk2 Note from BRS_02 song (ပုံနှိပ်နံ့ဝတီန်ကြိုး)

Figure (2) The power spectrum of 1-Pauk2 notes (a) 1-Pauk2 Note of Dr Maung Maung kha Pattalar (b) 1-Pauk2 Note from BRS_02 song (ပုံနှိပ်နံ့ဝတီန်ကြိုး)

Figure (3) The spectrogram of 1-Pauk2 notes (a) 1-Pauk2 Note of Dr Maung Maung kha Pattalar (b) 1-Pauk2 Note from BRS_02 song (ပုံနှိပ်နံ့ဝတီန်ကြိုး)

Conclusion

The tuning of the middle octave of three different Pattalars is varied in the range between musical significant pitch changes. The tuning of three different songs are also well tempered with the traditional music scale. However some notes are varied close to a semitone. Therefore the tuning of Pattalar is not consistent.

Although the pitch of the same note has the same frequency value, the wave form, power spectrum, and spectrogram are not identical. The solution of this problem is timbre, which make a unique sound of musical instrument. Therefore to determine the timbre of Bamboo Pattalar, a well developed body of signal processing analysis and synthesis techniques will be developed and decomposed the sound in future study.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my sincere thanks to Professor Dr Aye Aye Tun, Rector, Bago University, for her kind permission to carry out this work. I am also very grateful to express my sincere thanks to Professor Dr Yin Yin Than, Pro-Rector, Bago University, for her kind permission to carry out this work. I would like to express my sincere thanks to Professor Dr Khin Htoo, Head of Department of Physics, Bago University, for her encouragement for this work.

References

- Muriel C Williamson. (2000). *The Burmese Harp; Its classical music, tunings and modes*, Centre for South - East Asian Studies, Northern Illinois University.
- Dr Maung Maung Kha. (1963). *An Acoustical Analysis of the Vibrations of Bamboo Bars Used in Pattalars*, Journal of the Burma Research Society.
- Dr Tin Win, U Khin Maung Tin. (2018). *Investigating the Traditional Tunings of Saung Gauk (Burmese Arched Harp)*.
- Li Tan. (2008). *Digital Signal Processing Fundamentals and Applications*, DeVry University
- Julius O. Smith III. (2011). *Spectral Audio Signal Processing*, Centre for Computer Research in Music and Acoustic.